

DAFINET WORKSHOP
IN COLLABORATION WITH
BANGFISH AND PARAFISHCONTROL

SECURING FISH HEALTH IN WILD AND CULTURED FISH:
FROM PANGAS AND TILAPIAS VIA CARPS
AND PERCIDS TO SALMONIDS

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The relationship between water quality parameters and phytoplankton abundance in pangasius (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) and tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) ponds in Bangladesh

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Phytoplankton and zooplankton retort rapidly to any alterations in nutrient changes in water bodies indicating the growing nutrient pollution. On one hand where phytoplankton serves as food source, on the other hand some forms causes fish poisoning due to release of toxins during blooms.

The present study was carried out to analyze the water quality and plankton diversity of 4 selected pangasius (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) and tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) ponds from two different regions of Bangladesh; Bogra and Khulna. Monthly sampling was done for a period of 12 months, July 2016 to June 2017. Samples were analyzed for physico-chemical parameters. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of plankton. Plankton populations in the water of the experimental ponds were found to be consisted of 91 genera belonging 94 species under 13 planktonic groups composed of 9 groups of phytoplankton and 4 groups of zooplankton. Temperature, nitrate, phosphate, ammonia were positively correlated and pH, DO, transparency were negatively correlated with the plankton abundance. Results shows that the water is fairly good for fish culture. Nutrients of water enhanced the plankton growth which can lead to bloom. Therefore, it needs some corrective measures to maintain the water chemistry of the pond which will help to keep the plankton community in control.